

Supplementary Figure 1: Kaplan-Meier survival analyses for Disease free survival (DSF) in different histological subtypes of cervical cancer (p=0.088)

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Supplementary Figure 2 A S1: Kaplan-Meier survival analyses for disease free survival (DFS) and OS according to low immune

infiltration (A), moderate infiltration (B) or strong infiltration (C) in squamous cell cervical carcinoma cases

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